

CHEOPS

Very High-Power Building Blocks

HORIZON EUROPE PROJECT

CHEOPS Very High-Power Building Blocks

The project has received a co-funding from the European Union under the grant agreement 101082532.

The main objective of this project is to design, develop and test overall system architecture against these various mission use cases. The project CHEOPS VHP BB complements ongoing thruster-focused development activities with research and development on the future use of very high-power Hall thruster systems. The project will use a robust and cost-effective approach to qualification, manufacturability of critical components subject to wear, typically the discharge chamber and cathode and the ability to envisage alternative propellants and power sources.

Mission use case building block

Define detailed throttle profiles for a range of exploratory and IOS missions that will use very high power (VHP) Hall thrusters.

Architectural building blocks

Determine the most suitable architecture for VHP Hall thruster systems depending on the mission scenario, and compatible with a wide operational range.

Qualification building blocks

Establish recommendations to reduce uncertainties on failure mechanism models and identify appropriate diagnostic techniques.

Technology building blocks

Demonstrate the feasibility of using additive manufacturing techniques to produce a large discharge chamber. Improve the maturity up to TRL6 of a 50/100A cathode.

Co-funded by
the European Union

Contribution of the project towards

Wider impacts of the work programme

CHEOPS-VHP-BB will contribute to the various expected outcomes. In particular, it will help to strengthen, in the medium term, the European capacity to compete worldwide in electric propulsion satellites and missions.

Foster competitiveness of space systems

Reinforce EU capacity to access to space

Evolution of Space and ground infrastructures for Galileo/EGNOS

Business development, acceleration and upscaling of start-ups

Potential increase in EU market shares and new satellite contracts

Knowledge transfer - academic courses in Space Technologie

Linked projects

CHEOPS MP & CHEOPS LP projects

Electric propulsion systems (EPS) use electrical power to accelerate a propellant. Compared to chemical propellants, they are very lightweight and highly efficient. The EU-funded projects CHEOPS MP and CHEOPS LP aim to innovate in the field of propulsion systems and increase Europe's competitiveness in the satellite market.

CHEOPS Medium Power

CHEOPS Low Power

Co-funded by the European Union

Need for this project

The global space community is becoming increasingly interested in planetary explorations to the Moon and Mars, in near Earth orbit asteroid avoidance, in mining and in-orbit servicing missions. In-orbit servicing mission scenarios span a broad range of applications to improve the quality of service in space and include existing satellite life-extension operations, salvage, relocation, de-orbiting, robotics, space situational awareness and logistics. Thus, cost-effective and reliable solutions are needed.

The European Space industry must catch up

In the race to the Moon and Mars, as well as other lucrative commercial missions within earth's orbit beyond 2030, the European Space industry must catch up with the US. Studies within Europe have already been initiated for the incremental development of 20-kW class Hall thrusters, such as the FP7 HiPER project, which produced the PPS® 20k ML thruster up to TRL4, FP7 CHEOPS project, which permitted SITAEL to develop their 20kW HET, ESA projects allowing UNIPI to develop their nested multi-channel TANDEM thruster or the ongoing H2020 ASPIRE project led by SITAEL.

Research must be

anticipated now Given the challenges and the opportunities that VHP present, research such as the CHEOPS-VHP-BB consortium proposes must be anticipated now ahead of its effective deployment in 2030-40. Project activities will complement ongoing thruster-focused development activities with research and development on crucial building blocks essential for the future use of VHP Hall thruster systems: overall system architecture against various mission use cases, robust and cost-effective approach to qualification using Probabilistic Failure Analysis, manufacturability of critical components subject to wear, notably the discharge chamber and cathode and the ability to envisage alternative propellants and power sources for future missions.

Organisations behind the project

CHEOPS VHP BB consortium

The project consortium comprises 7 partners from 4 different European countries representing research centres, university, SMEs and one of the leading space industry organisations.

The aim of the project

Roles of the partners in the project

Safran Spacecraft Propulsion (France)

Project coordinator, who is also responsible for developing technological building blocks as well as methodologies for future sustainable qualification.

www.safran-group.com

Aerospazio Tecnologie SRL (Italy)

Responsible for diagnostic development, testing and test analysis.

www.aerospazio.com

University of Pisa (Italy)

Responsible for investigation of novel and outstanding solutions for the thruster's discharge chambers and anodes.

www.dici.unipi.it

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the European Union

The Leibniz Institute of Surface Engineering (IOM) (Germany)

Responsible for adaptation and use of Advanced Electric Propulsion Diagnostic platform for thruster testing.

www.iom-leipzig.de

Centre national de la recherche scientifique (CNRS) (France)

Responsible for plasma-wall interaction studies by laser diagnostics and for erosion modelling.

www.icare.cnrs.fr

Thales Alenia Space France SAS (France)

Responsible for mission analysis and requirement definition.

www.thalesgroup.com

WIT Berry (Latvia)

Responsible for project's communication and dissemination strategy and activities.

www.witberry.eu

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